

EURL

PUBLIC HEALTH

FOOD- AND WATER-BORNE BACTERIA

The EU Reference Laboratory in Public Health on Food- and waterborne bacteria (EURL-PH-FWDB) supports national reference laboratories in strengthening diagnostics, surveillance and response to cross-border threats from key food- and waterborne bacteria.

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Funded by
the European Union

The EU Reference Laboratory for Public Health on Food- and Waterborne Bacteria (EURL-PH -FWDB) is funded by the European Union under the EU4Health programme.

The consortium consists of public health institutes in Denmark, the Netherlands and Italy and works in close coordination with ECDC.

Coordinate and strengthen collaboration between the network laboratories

Provide targeted training and technical support

Foster cross-sectoral and global collaboration

Pathogens in scope

Listeria monocytogenes

Salmonella spp.

Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC)

Campylobacter spp.

Shigella spp.

Vibrio spp.

Yersinia spp. (excl. *Y. pestis*)

Core activities

EURL-PH-FWDB supports national reference laboratories (NRLs) in the EU/EEA countries by providing scientific and technical expertise related to food- and waterborne pathogens. Main EURL activities include:

- Scientific and technical support to network laboratories
- External quality assessments (EQAs)
- Scientific advice and outbreak support to ECDC
- Trainings

